

Locating Nazeer Akbarabadi in the Tradition of Nature Poetry: A Study of Nature as Shared Human Inheritance in Select Poems

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20328922>

Abstract

Nazeer Akbarabadi, popularly known as ‘people’s poet’ holds a place of distinction in Urdu poetry for his celebration of everyday life, common people, and the natural world. His poems treat nature as an important and democratic force that can help build shared values. This is different from the traditional Persian-influenced lyrical tradition, which mostly centered on courtly love and abstract ideas. In Nazeer’s poetic world nature provides a shared cultural environment that unites diverse communities across religious, social, and economic divides. His poems explore the life of ordinary people, seasonal cycles, fruits, animals, and festivals rooted in natural elements, symbolising coexistence, equality, and mutual dependence. According to Nazeer, nature is a resource that unites everyone and serves as a moral, social, and spiritual teacher, reminding people of their shared roots, humility, and joy. A thorough textual analysis of the select poems tries to establish the idea how nature plays an inherently communal and ethical role in his poetic vision, resisting division and asserting a harmonious social fabric. Nazeer thus emerges as a poet of inclusivity, whose ecology-centric worldview has enduring relevance in contemporary times marked by communal fragmentation.

Key Words: Nature, Co-existence, People, Communal, Harmony

In literary discourse, nature refers to the visible and material manifestations of the universe that are not the result of human craftsmanship. Grass, greenery, gardens, canals, meandering streams, waterfalls, valleys, flowers, birds and animals, and the mountains standing in all their majesty—these are all testament to nature’s craftsmanship and eloquent expressions of the perfection of Divine creation. Human effort plays no role in their making, and it is precisely for this reason that their beauty remains timeless. Objects fashioned by human hands inevitably lose their charm after a certain period and their brilliance begins to fade; but the allure of nature retains an enduring and inexhaustible capacity to delight the human spirit. A contemporary Urdu poet, Shahid Zaki, articulates this idea succinctly in his couplet:

Sho-uri koshishein manzar bigaad deti hain

Wahi hasin hai jo besakhta bana hua hai

Conscious efforts every scene distort

Beautiful is effortless, Nature's art.

Long back Rousseau, the French philosopher and champion of the idea of 'Back to Nature' affirmed how human intervention in the scheme of nature always plays a corruptive role. In his famous treatise on the nature of education *Emile*, he holds that "Everything is good as it comes from the hands of the Author of Nature; but everything degenerates in the hands of man" (Payne 1). Nature offers man in plenty but led by his greed, man himself is responsible for his suffering by constantly being engaged in the process of destroying and destructing what is of utmost importance to him. One cannot but agree with Wordsworth when he expresses his concern: "The World is too much with us; late and soon, / Getting and spending, we lay waste our powers;/ Little we see in Nature that is ours" (*The World* 1-3).

Literature, especially poetry offers abundant examples of the depiction of natural beauty and the description of landscape. While the poetry of ancient Greece and Rome is largely grounded in religious themes, moral ideals, and heroic narratives, it is by no means devoid of representations of nature. From the Renaissance English literature to the modern period, poets have consistently drawn upon nature as a central subject of poetic expression. It is, however, during the Romantic movement that nature was elevated to an unprecedented status. Among the Romantic poets, William Wordsworth stands out in particular for assigning nature a profound philosophical and emotional significance:

One impulse from a vernal wood
May teach you more of man,
Of moral evil and of good,
Than all the sages can. (*Tables* 25-28)

The conception of nature in American poetry, beginning with nature as a manifestation of the Creator and a source of spiritual solace and emotional equilibrium, expanded to incorporate the diverse experiences, struggles, and moral dilemmas of human life. As a result, nature came to function as a mirror reflecting the dynamic relationship between humanity and the natural world. This is best reflected in Robert Frost's celebrated poem "Stopping by Woods on a Snowy Evening". In this poem, the serene and visually arresting image of snow-covered woods is transformed into a symbolic landscape. The recurring line, "And miles to go before I sleep" (225), underscores the ethical tension between personal desire and communal commitment, suggesting that nature, while alluring, must be reconciled with human duty. The poet is eager to enjoy the blessings of nature but the call of duty must push him to disengage him from his desire to stay back. Thus, the poet treats nature as a reflective surface for the human–nature relationship.

French poetry offers some of the finest examples of the representation of nature. Starting with the depiction of nature through the beauty of rivers, rural landscapes, and the changing seasons, the treatment extends to the manifestation of divine power within nature. Nature also becomes a space of refuge—a means of escape from the bitterness and tensions of society, and a source of peace and solace in its nurturing embrace. At the same time, nature functions as a symbol for the expression of inner states of mind and emotional experiences, and, in the modern age, it increasingly serves as a medium for articulating eco-critical concerns.

Charles D' Orleans' "The season has shed its mantle" welcomes the arrival of the Spring season as a time of renewal when nature discards its heavy cloak and ornaments herself with embroidery, suggesting delicacy, colour, and careful artistry, pointing toward blossoming flowers, fresh foliage, and the intricate beauty of Spring:

The season has shed its mantle
Of wind, cold and rain,
And has clothed itself in embroidery.
In gleaming sunshine, bright and fair. (17)

In German poetry, nature is represented through multiple interrelated dimensions: the depiction of natural beauty, the symbolic articulation of human emotions, the expression of trauma and suffering produced by the Second World War, and, in the modern period, a sustained engagement with issues concerning the survival and preservation of nature itself.

From the Romantic celebration of organic unity in poets like Johann Wolfgang von Goethe, to the inward, metaphysical landscapes of Rainer Maria Rilke, and the historical anguish articulated by Paul Celan, German poetry traces an evolving relationship between man, nature, and history—one that moves from harmony to rupture, and finally toward ecological and moral urgency in the contemporary world. Clemens Brentano in his "The Spinner's Song" aligns his emotional response of parting from his beloved to the song of the nightingale changing from a delightful note to a sorrowful one, emphasising the idea of the bond that nature and man share:

When our two hearts were one,
Of joy sang the nightingale;
Now all its changeful tale
Is but that thou art gone. (95)

However, the poetic engagement with nature cannot be viewed as an exclusive feature of the European literary tradition. Across the globe, one encounters refined and enduring models of nature-description in which poets consciously turn toward the natural world in search

of spiritual tranquillity, inward reflection, moral elevation, and philosophical insight, while simultaneously satisfying their aesthetic impulse.

Within the Chinese poetic tradition, in particular, nature occupies a central and defining position as a site of introspection and meditative awareness, where the external landscape becomes inseparable from the poet's inner consciousness. Wang Wei in one of his poems "Joys of the Country" suggests that spiritual fulfillment lies in attunement with the natural world rather than in public life or political ambition. Nature in this poem functions as an ethical and spiritual alternative to the artificiality of urban and official existence.

Lush, lush, fragrant grasses in autumn green;
tall tall, towering pines in summer cold;
cows and sheep come home by themselves to village lanes;
little boys know nothing of capped and robed officials. (201)

Li Po's "Still Night Thoughts" is remarkable for its simplicity and emotional depth. In just four lines, the poet establishes an intimate and organic relationship between nature and human consciousness.

Moonlight in front of my bed
I took it for frost on the ground!
I lift my eyes to watch the mountain moon,
lower them and dream of home. (210)

Japanese poetry accords a central and almost indispensable place to nature. In fact, haiku, a distinctive poetic form of Japan, derives its very imagery and meaning from the natural world. In haiku, nature is not merely a background setting but a primary vehicle of meaning. Through images of seasons and landscape, the poet gestures toward larger ideas like transience, solitude, and harmony with the cosmos. Gessht Jukei in the poem "Drinking on a Peaceful Evening in Spring" beautifully captures the sight of man blending into nature. The speaker's inner being expands to match the cosmos. Moonlight is not just experienced; it is consumed with the wine in the cup. This is a unique moment of man turning into nature:

Drinking wine before the blossoms, I sit in the
spring wind; in the late night air it's quiet, but inside the
banqueting goes on.
I sip up the drop of moonlight in my wine cup in

one gulp;

my breast is now like the sky: The Palace of

Boundless Cold. (331)

Matsuo Basho, the most famous of all Japanese poets, through his haiku “Village People” shows village people working in the paddy fields, expressing a rhythm of life created out of labour and recognition of the wealth of contentment and cheerfulness that being in tune with nature brings: “Village people/making poems in the paddies— /their own capital!” (355).

In African poetry, nature constitutes an inseparable part of the traditional African rituals and customs, religious beliefs, spiritual experiences, and everyday life. Natural elements such as forests, rivers, animals, seasons, and landscapes are deeply embedded in indigenous cultural practices, often symbolising ancestral presence, communal memory, and moral order. At the same time, African poetry, particularly, African American poetry frequently employs nature to articulate the historical and psychological impact of the colonial experience, making the natural world a witness to displacement, exploitation, and cultural rupture.

Unlike the English Romantic tradition, African poetry presents world where nature is not merely a refuge of peace and harmony but also a site of struggle, suffering, and survival. Droughts, harsh climates, scarred landscapes, and disrupted ecosystems become metaphors for political oppression, social injustice, and existential anguish. Askia M.Toure in “Floodtide” expresses the ferocious and destructive side of nature:

the rain comes

and washes the green mountains;

floods the cotton land,

the rain comes,

ruins the tobacco,

kills the livestock; makin' a mock'ry

of our prayers

for rain.

the killer rain comes:

the river is a ragin' madman.

the river breaks our hearts. (184)

Arabic poetry primarily records the Arab culture, and its collective national and tribal consciousness. Much like classical European poetry, it foregrounds themes of bravery, valour, warfare, and heroism. However, it would be inaccurate to suggest that nature remains peripheral to the Arabic poetic imagination. On the contrary, nature imagery is deeply woven into its poetic tradition. Particularly evocative are descriptions of the desert landscape—its shimmering sands under moonlight, the stillness and mystery of the night, the scenes of sunrise and sunset encountered during journeys on camels and horses. As you read the poem “you roam with the poet over the varied domain of Nature in all its freshness, artlessness, and freedom” (Muir qtd. in Clouston 3).

Moreover, classical Arabic poetry developed distinctive genres such as the *qasida* (praise) and *hajwa'* (satire), both of which frequently employ images drawn from nature. In panegyrics, the grandeur and beauty of nature are invoked to elevate the praised individual, while in satire, the harshness, barrenness, or ferocity of the natural world becomes a metaphor for moral deficiency or social critique. In “one of the earliest, and certainly the most eminent, of pre-Islamic poets, Imru'al-Qays” (Farrin 1) in one of his “prized odes (Mu'allaqat) from the pre-Islamic era that were supposedly inscribed in gold letters and hung on the walls of the Ka'ba in Mecca” (2), praises his horse, using imagery from nature: “A chestnut stallion, whose saddle pad slips from his back as rainwater cascading slips from the surface of a smooth stone”(13).

Persian poetic tradition is deeply imbued with Sufi thought, and major poets such as Rumi, Jami, Hafiz, and Saadi consistently employ nature as a symbol of spiritual perception and metaphysical awareness. Elements of the natural world—gardens, flowers, wine, seasons, and celestial imagery—are used to gesture towards transcendence, divine love, and the soul's journey towards truth.

In contrast, modern Persian poetry witnesses a significant shift in thematic concerns and aesthetic strategies. Nature imagery is increasingly mobilised to articulate inner psychological states, existential anxieties, and questions of identity. In particular, poets such as Forugh Farrokhzad employ natural imagery to explore feminine subjectivity and the tensions between selfhood and society.

In her poem “Later On” Farrokhzad looks at death as a means of release from existential emptiness of life. Nature appears as maternal and compassionate in the form of the earth inviting the poet to come for the final sleep. Death becomes a return, echoing ancient notions of unity between human life and the natural world.

The earth invites me into its arms,
folks gather to entomb me there
perhaps at midnight my lovers
place above me wreaths of many roses. (9)

In the Indian context, any discussion of the poetic treatment of nature must take into account the country's long-standing multilingual and multicultural character. India has historically been a space of interaction among diverse languages, literary traditions, and cultural systems, resulting in a composite and syncretic civilization. Consequently, nature has occupied a privileged position in the poetic expressions of nearly all languages spoken and written in the subcontinent. What is particularly significant is that alongside Sanskrit and the later Indo-Aryan languages, traditions of Arabic and Persian poetry also flourished in India, while a rich body of regional literatures developed simultaneously.

As a consequence of India's colonial experience, the English language also took firm root and gradually flourished as a medium of literary expression. In the works of poets like Toru Dutt, Sarojini Naidu, and Ravindra Nath Tagore nature is rendered through indigenous images of seasons, flowers, rivers, and birds, often intertwined with emotion, nationalism, and lyrical sensibility: "This little flute of a reed thou hast carried over hills and dales, and hast breathed through it melodies eternally new" (Tagore 1).

In classical Sanskrit literature, the poetry of Kalidasa offers one of the most celebrated examples of refined nature poetry. His lyric poem *Meghaduta* (The Cloud Messenger) transforms the monsoon cloud into a messenger that bridges physical distance and emotional longing. Through detailed and evocative descriptions of landscapes, seasons, rivers, and mountains, Kalidasa integrates nature with human emotion, particularly *viraha* (the pain of separation), thereby establishing nature as an active participant in human experience:

When thy thunder stirs the earth to burgeon with mushroom parasols,
That music, sweet to the ears of royal swans, will rouse their longing
For Manasa Lake; they will form thine escort in the air to Mount Kailasa,
Gathering the tips of lotus-stalks to stay them on their flight. (15)

In Urdu literature also, the representation of nature extends far beyond a mere descriptive account of these external forms. It encompasses the evocation of both concealed and explicit emotions, the authentic sensibilities, and the deeper experiential truths that natural objects awaken within the human consciousness. From the earliest stages of Urdu poetic tradition, nature has occupied a position of marked significance, consistently attracting the attention of poets across periods. This significance is not restricted to any single genre. One could find it in all major poetic forms in Urdu including *ghazal* which is highly sophisticated and nuanced both in terms of structure and theme. Although predominantly subjective and having amorous orientations, it frequently incorporates images and motifs drawn from the natural world. In fact, the poet draws heavily on the manifestations of nature to celebrate the beauty of the beloved. In other classical poetic forms, such as the *masnavi*, *marsiya*, and *qasida*, the representation of nature assumes an even more integral and structural role, often functioning as a foundational aesthetic device.

With regard to the *Nazm*, it is noteworthy that from Quli Qutub Shah and Nazeer Akbarabadi to contemporary practitioners, poets have persistently situated nature at the conceptual and imaginative centre of their work. The *Nazm*, moreover, commands a distinctive status: in every literary epoch, poets have engaged with nature in innovative ways, extracting new thematic possibilities, symbolic resonances, and artistic functions from its diverse manifestations. These evolving engagements are sufficiently rich and multidimensional to merit rigorous and focused critical study.

Nazeer Akbarabadi was born most likely between 1735 and 1740 in Delhi. Regarding his birth, Ram Babu Saksena records in his work *A History of Urdu Literature* that Nazeer was born in 1739, during the invasion of Delhi by Nadir Shah (140). Subsequently, he migrated to Agra with his mother, where he spent the greater part of his life. Unlike many poets of his time, Nazeer did not associate himself with any royal court. He received elementary education in Arabic and Persian but had access to the vernaculars especially, Braj Bhasha, Punjabi, Hindi, and chose to earn his livelihood as a teacher. In Agra, he was appointed tutor to the son of Lala Bilas Ram, undertaking teaching duties for a monthly remuneration of seventy rupees.

In the later years of his life, Nazeer suffered a paralytic stroke and passed away on 16 August 1830. Having lived a long life, he may be regarded as a contemporary of major classical poets such as Sauda, Mir Taqi Mir, and Khwaja Mir Dard. He also lived to witness the poetic era of later figures such as Insha Allah Khan, Jur'at, and Nasikh. Nevertheless, owing to his distinctly individual poetic temperament and thematic concerns, Nazeer remains singular and distinguished, standing apart from both his contemporaries and successors:

He was not a courtier, he neither eulogised the rich nor lampooned those of humbler station. As a poet of the common things of life he stands alone, for he writes of practically nothing else. King Muhammad Quli Qutb Shah does indeed speak of everyday matters, but he also writes a good deal in a more conventional style. (Baily 59)

One of Nazeer's most popular and aesthetically rich poems, *Barsat ki Baharen* (The Delights of the Monsoon), is closely associated with the experience of the rainy season. This long poem is a remarkable poetic canvas in which the monsoon (*barsat*) is transformed from a seasonal phenomenon into a total experience of life—natural, social, emotional, and spiritual. The sheer length of the poem in itself is quite meaningful: like the monsoon rain, it pours continuously, overwhelming the reader with sights, sounds, and sensations.

Clouds, rain, wind, lightning, rivers, greenery, birds, animals, and insects all participate in a vast, rhythmic movement. The recurring imagery of dripping roofs, flowing streams, dancing peacocks, croaking frogs, and singing birds creates a symphony of rain, where every element of nature seems alive and expressive. Through a careful and melodious choice of words, the poet depicts the monsoon landscape with such artistic dexterity that the reader begins to feel like an active participant in the scene itself:

haiñ is havā meñ kyā kyā barsāt kī bahāreñ

sabzoñ kī lahlahāhaT bāghāt kī bahāreñ

būñdoñ kī jhamjhamāvaT qatrāt kī bahāreñ

har baat ke tamāshe har ghaat kī bahāreñ

kyā kyā machī haiñ yaaro barsāt kī bahāreñ

The monsoon air what joy it brings!

The lush green fields in vibrant dance, the gardens all aflame.

The raindrops pattering, beads sparkling

Here a delight, there a game.

What revels, o friends, the monsoon brings!

Alongside this vivid pictorial quality, Nazeer also foregrounds the psychological relationship between nature and human emotion. While the monsoon ignites warmth and passion in the hearts of lovers, it simultaneously intensifies the anguish of those afflicted by separation, thereby revealing nature's dual emotional impact:

jo vasl meñ haiñ un ke juuDe mahak rahe haiñ

jhūloñ meñ jhūlte haiñ gahne jhamak rahe haiñ

jo dukh meñ haiñ so un ke siine phaḌak rahe haiñ

aaheñ nikal rahī haiñ aañsū Tapak rahe haiñ

kyā kyā machī haiñ yaaro barsāt kī bahāreñ

United in love, their braids with flowers fragrant

They sway upon the swings, their ornaments glow

Those in sorrow, their chests aflame with pain;

Sighs escape their lips, tears from eyes flow

O friends, what revels the monsoon brings!

One of Nazeer's greatest strengths lies in his refusal to romanticize nature uncritically. The monsoon brings pleasure—lush greenery, swinging lovers, music, wine, festivity, sensual delight—but it also brings hardship. Leaking roofs, collapsing huts, mud, insects, illness, and poverty appear with equal force. For the wealthy, rain enhances comfort and leisure; for the poor, it intensifies vulnerability. This coexistence of delight and distress makes the poem

deeply human and realistic. The monsoon becomes a metaphor for life itself: generous yet cruel, beautiful yet burdensome.

Despite these contrasting human responses, the poet discovers within this beautiful natural spectacle an occasion for praise and gratitude toward the Creator. The poem thus gestures beyond sensory delight to affirm the intrinsic bond between human beings and their Creator, suggesting that an awareness of divine presence within nature deepens both emotional experience and spiritual consciousness:

kyā kyā rakhe haiñ yārab sāmān terī qudrat

badle hai rañg kyā kyā har aan terī qudrat

sab mast ho rahe pahchān terī qudrat

tītar pukārte haiñ sub.hān terī qudrat

kyā kyā machī haiñ yaaro barsāt kī bahāreñ

What countless marvels holds, My Lord, Your power!

Every moment in myriad hues manifest

In raptures lost, all Your signs witness

The song of Your glory the partridge sings

O friends, what revels the monsoon brings!

The poem is extraordinary in its social range. Kings and beggars, lovers and ascetics, courtesans and housewives, the rich in mansions and the poor in huts—all find space in the poet's vision. Nazeer does not privilege one class over another; instead, he places all within the same rain-soaked world. This inclusive outlook reflects his democratic spirit and his closeness to everyday life. The monsoon acts as a great equalizer: everyone is touched by it, though not everyone experiences it in the same way. In this sense, the poem becomes a document of social reality, revealing class divisions while also emphasising shared human existence.

Nazeer emerges as a poet of humanity and celebration—a celebration in which human life attains harmony with nature. It is for this reason that even the most ordinary objects in his poetry become sources of joy and exhilaration. Moving beyond the narrow and restrictive confines of religion, politics, power, authority, race, class, and gender, Nazeer discovers pathways of delight and vitality in the everyday experiences of common human life. He is a distinctly Indian poet and a true representative of the *Ganga–Jamuni* cultural ethos. He is the poet of seasons and festivals, and his poetry is imbued with liveliness and vibrancy. This liveliness and vibrancy arise from his deep awareness that the true pleasure of life lies in living

it fully. Such an understanding becomes possible only when one discovers the relationship between the self, the universe, and the Creator of the universe. Once a poet attains this insight, the heart is filled with a capacious and generous love—one that embraces all shades of human existence. These diverse hues together form an aesthetic ideal whose realization strengthens the values of peace, harmony, and coexistence. This is best reflected in his poem *Holi Ki Baharen*, (The Revels of Holi) another remarkable poem by him.

An important aspect of *Holi ki Baharen* that deserves attention is the presence of nature at the very opening of the poem, signalled by the word Phagun, the month of Spring associated with Holi. It immediately situates the poem within a seasonal and natural framework. Nature here is not a passive background but the initiating force that sets the rhythm of festivity in motion. The shimmering of colours, the warmth in the air, and the sensory awakening associated with Spring prepare the ground for human celebration.

By beginning the poem with Phagun, Nazeer establishes an organic continuity between nature and culture. The joy of Holi appears as an extension of seasonal renewal: just as nature blossoms and overflows with colour, human emotions, bodies, and social life also break free from restraint. This alignment underscores Nazeer's belief that human pleasure, creativity, and communal bonding are deeply rooted in natural cycles. The festival does not violate nature; rather, it responds to it. Moreover, the invocation of Phagun subtly reinforces the poem's inclusive ethos. Seasonal change is universally experienced, cutting across religious and social divisions. In this sense, nature becomes a shared ground of existence, enabling collective participation and harmony. Thus, from its very first word, *Holi ki Baharen* affirms Nazeer's broader vision: life, nature, and human society are intertwined, and true festivity emerges when this harmony is fully realized:

jab phāgun rañg jhamakte hoñ tab dekh bahāreñ holī kī

aur daf ke shor khaḌakte hoñ tab dekh bahāreñ holī kī

pariyoñ ke rañg damakte hoñ tab dekh bahāreñ holī kī

ḳhum, shīshe, jaam, jhalakte hoñ tab dekh bahāreñ holī kī

mahbūb nashe meñ chakte hoñ tab dekh bahāreñ holī kī

When Phagan bursts in flashing hues, the revels of Holi behold

When drums resound and tambours clash, the revels of Holi behold

When damsels glow, gleam, and kill, the revels of Holi behold

When cups and crystal goblets spill, the revels of Holi behold

When lovers enjoy a drunken splash, the revels of Holi behold

The poem is one of the most striking examples of festive poetry in Urdu literature. It is notable for its linguistic vitality, vivid pictorial quality, carnivalesque spirit, and inclusive social vision. The poet freely blends Persianised Urdu with colloquial, bazaar-level speech, folk idiom, and everyday expressions. This deliberate mixing gives the poem immediacy and authenticity, allowing it to mirror lived reality rather than refined literary artifice. The poem is intensely picturesque, unfolding like a moving canvas of colour and sound. Visual imagery dominates—splashes of colour on clothes, flushed faces, goblets brimming with wine, gardens blooming—while auditory images of drums, anklets, clapping, and singing heighten the festive atmosphere. *Holi ki Baharen* exemplifies what may be called carnivality. Social norms, hierarchies, and moral restraints are temporarily suspended. Courtesans, revellers, musicians, drunkards, and common folk all occupy the same poetic space. The inclusion of bawdy humour, intoxication, and physical exuberance reflects a world turned upside down, where sanctioned disorder becomes a form of release. This festive inversion challenges elite literary decorum and celebrates life in its raw, unfiltered abundance.

But beyond this exuberance, the poem carries a deeper social significance. Holi emerges as a shared cultural event, transcending religious, social, and class boundaries. Muslims and Hindus, elites and commoners, men and women participate together in collective joy. Nazeer's depiction affirms India's composite culture, where festivals function as spaces of coexistence and social bonding. The poem thus subtly reinforces communal harmony without overt moralizing.

Nazeer consistently incorporated the lived experiences of everyday life into his poetry. He had a keen fondness for leisure and recreation, music, physical activity, fairs, markets, and festivals, and these interests find frequent expression in his verse. Known for his wit, playful imagination, and gentle, courteous manner of speech, Nazeer enjoyed equal popularity among both Muslims and Hindus, a fact that underscores his inclusive and humanist outlook.

It has, however, been alleged by some critics that elements of obscenity and crudeness appear in parts of his poetry. Such criticisms largely pertain to his early youthful phase. With the maturation of his consciousness, Nazeer's poetic temperament underwent a significant transformation, and his later work reflects the sensibility of a Sufi-minded ascetic, marked by spiritual depth, ethical reflection, and a renunciation of excess. His poem *Aadmi Nama* (The Poem on Man) is one of the most representative and powerful expressions of his humanistic vision.

In *Aadmi Nama*, Nazeer presents a panoramic portrait of humanity in all its diversity and contradiction. The poem deliberately dismantles social hierarchies by repeatedly foregrounding the word "aadmi" (human being), thereby asserting the essential equality of all people regardless of class, profession, wealth, religion, or status. Kings and beggars, saints and sinners, scholars and fools, believers and infidels, rulers and executioners, —all are equally "aadmi". This repetition works like a hammer: each blow reinforces the truth that human contradictions exist within the same species, not outside it. All are shown as variations of the

same human condition. This levelling impulse reflects Nazeer's resistance to elitist literary conventions and his commitment to a democratic poetic ethos:

duniyā meñ pādshah hai so hai vo bhī aadmī

aur muflis-o-gadā hai so hai vo bhī aadmī

zardār-e-be-navā hai so hai vo bhī aadmī

nemat jo khā rahā hai so hai vo bhī aadmī

TukḌe chabā rahā hai so hai vo bhī aadmī

In this world, a king is human still,

So is the pauper, poor and ill;

The rich man too is but a man,

And he who lives on gifts, again;

One feasts on plenty, one on crumbs

Yet each is human, when all's done.

Nazeer's vision of humanity is profoundly non-idealized. Humans are capable of sanctity and cruelty, devotion and arrogance, wisdom and deception. Saints and harmless people coexist with tyrants like Pharaoh and Nimrod; mosque-builders coexist with thieves who steal shoes from the places of worship. The poem insists that virtue and vice are not separate human categories but shared possibilities. Even religious institutions are human-made and human-run—and therefore subject to human weakness. By highlighting this, Nazeer subtly critiques hypocrisy while affirming shared responsibility.

One of the poem's greatest strengths lies in its documentary realism. Nazeer catalogues daily professions, rituals, ceremonies, markets, marriages, funerals, travel, commerce, entertainment, crime, and punishment. The world of the poem is bustling, noisy, and ordinary—closer to a street than a court. This grounding in lived reality gives the poem a democratic ethos.

Nature, though not always explicitly foregrounded, functions implicitly as a shared ground of existence: all human beings are born into the same world, subject to the same natural laws of time, change, decay, and death. In this sense, *Aadmi Nama* aligns closely with both humanist and proto-eco-critical thought, emphasizing interdependence, humility, and the fragility of human pretensions. *Aadmi Nama* thus stands not merely as a social satire but as a philosophical meditation on humanity itself—one that anticipates modern concerns with equality, coexistence, and shared responsibility in a common world.

India has historically remained a confluence of diverse civilizations and cultures. The Indian subcontinent has always upheld the ideals of unity, peace, harmony, and mutual coexistence even during times of upheaval. Sages, seers, ascetics, saints, spiritual guides, poets, and philosophers alike have consistently preached values such as peace, harmony and coexistence. Rising above the boundaries of language, region, religion, and race, these figures articulated a shared moral and spiritual vision. Nazeer carries this humanistic tradition forward in his poetry. At a time when his contemporaries were largely preoccupied with linguistic refinement, formal poetic conventions, and the notion of linguistic purity, Nazeer deliberately turned his attention toward the lived realities of ordinary people. By representing everyday life in the language of the common masses, he introduced a new breadth and democratic spirit into Urdu poetry, particularly expanding the expressive possibilities of *Nazm*.

This conscious departure from the dominant literary norms of his age, however, resulted in his marginalization. He “was given the cold shoulder by the earlier critics for being an eccentric who did not fit into the scheme of traditional poetry” (Sadiq 154). His poetry, which resisted elite aesthetics and courtly exclusivity, failed to gain immediate critical recognition. Significantly, Muhammad Husain Azad, in his canonical literary history *Aab-e-Hayat*, did not even deem it necessary to mention Nazeer’s contribution. This critical neglect underscores the tension between popular literary expression and canonical standards, a gap that was only bridged in later literary historiography, when Nazeer’s pioneering role in humanistic and socially inclusive poetry came to be fully acknowledged.

Although he was a victim of neglect, the poetic tradition established by Nazeer Akbarabadi proved so influential that succeeding generations of poets could scarcely remain untouched by it. Poets such as Altaf Husain Hali and Muhammad Iqbal, among other significant figures, drew upon Nazeer’s expansive vision when articulating the relationship between nature and human life. While their ideological frameworks and poetic objectives differed, their engagement with themes of social reality, ethical consciousness, and harmony between humanity and the natural world reveals a clear indebtedness to Nazeer’s mode of expression. Thus, Nazeer’s legacy extends beyond stylistic innovation to shape a broader poetic sensibility in Urdu literature—one that foregrounds human values, social awareness, and an organic relationship between nature and life.

Note: I have referred to *Rekhat* (regkhta.org) for the excerpts from the select poems of Nazir Akbaradi and one Urdu couplet by Shahid Zaki and translated them in English

Works Cited

Akbarabadi, Nazeer. “Barsaat Ki Baharen” *Rekhta*.

---. “www.rekhta.org/nazms/barsaat-kii-bahaaren-hain-is-havaa-men-kyaa-kyaa-barsaat-kii-bahaaren-nazeer-akbarabadi-nazms?lang=ur”

---. “Holi Ki Baharen” *Rekhta*.

<https://www.rekhta.org/nazms/holii-kii-bahaaren-jab-phaagun-rang-jhamakte-hon-tab-dekh-bahaaren-holii-kii-nazeer-akbarabadi-nazms?lang=ur>

---. Aadmi Naama” *Rekhta*.

www.rekhta.org/nazms/aadmii-naama-duniyaa-men-paadshah-hai-so-hai-vo-bhii-aadmii-nazeer-akbarabadi-nazms?lang=ur

Baily, T. Grahame. *A History of Urdu Literature*. The Heritage of India Series, Oxford University Press, 1932.

Basho, Matsuo. “Village People” “Drinking on a Peaceful Evening in Spring” *Traditional Japanese Poetry: An Anthology*, translated by Steven D. Carter, Stanford University Press, 1991.

Brentano, Clemens. “The Spinner’s Song” *An Anthology of German Poetry from Holderlin to Rilke in English Translation*, edited by Angel Flores, Anchor Books Doubleday & Company, Inc., 1960, p.95.

Clouston, W.A. *Arabian Poetry*. Global Grey, 1881.

Farrokhzad, Forugh. “Later on.” *Remembering the Flight: Twenty Poems by Forugh Farrokhzad*, translated by Ahmad Karimi-Hakkak, Ketab Corp., 2004, p.9.

Farrin, Raymond. *Abundance from the Desert: Classical Arab Poetry*. Middle East Literature in Translation, Syracuse University Press, 2011.

Frost, Robert. “Stopping by Woods on a Snowy Evening” *The Poetry of Robert Frost*, edited by Edward Connery Lathem, Jonathan Cape Ltd, 1971, p.225.

Jukei, Gessht “Drinking on a Peaceful Evening in Spring” *Traditional Japanese Poetry: An Anthology*, translated by Steven D. Carter, Stanford University Press, 1991.

Kalidasa. *The Cloud Messenger*. Translated by Franklin and Eleanor Edgerton, The University of Michigan, 1964.

Orleans, Charles D’ “The season has shed its mantle” *Introduction to French Poetry: A Dual- Language Book*, edited by Stanley Appelbaum, Dover Publications, Inc., 1969, p.17.

Payne, William H. *Rousseau’s Emile or Treatise on Education*. D. Appleton and Company, 1918.

Po, Li “Still Night Thoughts” *The Columbia Book of Chinese Poetry: From Early Times to the Thirteenth Century*, translated and Edited by Richard Burton, Columbia University Press, 1984.

- Sadiq, Muhammad. *A History of Urdu Literature*. Delhi, Oxford India Press, 1995.
- Saksena, Ram Babu. *A History of Urdu Literature*. Ram Narain Lal Publisher and Bookseller, 1940.
- Tagore, Rabindranath. *Gitanjali*. The Macmillan Company, 1915.
- Toure, Askia M. "Floodtide" *Four Centuries of African American Nature Poetry*, edited by Camille T. Dungy, The University of Georgia Press, 2009, p.184.
- Wei, Wang. "Joys of the Country" *The Columbia Book of Chinese Poetry: From Early Times to the Thirteenth Century*, translated and Edited by Richard Burton, Columbia University Press, 1984.
- Wordsworth, William. "The World Is Too Much With Us" *Poetry Foundation*.
<https://www.poetryfoundation.org/poems/45564/the-world-is-too-much-with-us>
- . "Tables Turned" *Poetry Foundation*.
<https://www.poetryfoundation.org/poems/45557/the-tables-turned>
- Zaki, Shahid. *Rekhta*.
<https://www.rekhta.org/ghazals/jidhar-bhii-dekhiye-ik-raasta-banaa-huaa-hai-shahid-zaki-ghazals?lang=ur>